

Learning Organization An Approach to the Development of Technical High School Administration

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Abstract

The learning organization aims to stimulate the mental capacity and structured thinking of all employees of the institution And so that school staff can support this new model and apply it.

The Current research has used the Descriptive Methodology aimed at describing facts and events occurring in the present, and is concerned with circumstances, relationships, common practices, opinions and beliefs This Methodology was used because of its relevance to the nature of the study, which requires the collection of evidence and statistical analysis to extract the required results.

Keywords, technical secondary education, Learning Organization

Introduction to the Research

Education is considered the foundation of comprehensive development, as it represents a latent treasure within society and a significant means to eliminate unemployment. It provides qualified scientific personnel capable of research, innovation, development, and achieving technical progress in various aspects of life, as well as continuous improvement in living standards.

Technical education is one of the main tools for achieving comprehensive development programs; indeed, it is considered the engine of development. If education is the key to the development strategy, then technical education is the primary key that can change the world of work and the economy and improve the quality of life. With its various types, it strives to prepare the skilled workforce necessary to serve economic and social development plans, which are directly attributed to the labor market.

Most countries around the world are adopting plans to develop technical education to link it with economic development plans and work on transforming the individual from a passive recipient to a productive and innovative person capable of adapting to the changing demands of work through acquiring applicable professional and practical skills.

In Egypt, technical secondary education represents the fundamental entry point for economic development and its needs for modern and diverse means, methods of work, and specializations. Industrial education has taken upon itself the task of preparing the educated individual And the trainee on sound foundations, so that he can find the skilled workforce a place in the labor markets, both domestically and abroad.

The Technical Secondary Education Authority in Egypt is considered one of the state's responsibilities, which supervises it technically, administratively, and financially directly. Its departments are based on central foundations, and technical secondary education in Egypt plays a fundamental role in meeting the needs of society for skilled labor according to the specializations required by the plans and programs of economic and social development.

The learning organization approach provides a means to increase the ability to compete in the face of rapid global changes, which leads to the organization's ability to continue learning and improving performance. Some researchers call for a "learning organization" that values learning and education, and involves all employees in the continuous improvement process. Everyone bears their responsibilities collectively, the manager transforms into a learning leader, provides learning opportunities, offers motivating feedback, and fosters trust and success. This makes the learning process a continuous strategic operation within the overall school system, in which everyone participates with their full potential without limitations.

Research Problem:

The reports indicated that technical secondary school administrations do not participate in the planning process for renewal and lack importance when it comes to implementation, as they do not provide the necessary data for planning and evaluation. The school administration also lacks sufficient authority to evaluate the performance of staff within the school, especially teachers, and the idea of self-evaluation is absent.

educational institutions – and among them technical secondary schools – are not developed internally by those within the organization; rather, any development that occurs within them comes from outside.

As some management literature such as Thomas and Allen's study indicated, there are several justifications that lead to competition in adopting the concepts

and characteristics of learning organizations, and then applying and maintaining them across various levels of development and change

Based on the above, the learning organization is considered an entry point for development in educational organizations at the administrative and academic levels, especially in light of contemporary changes and the technological and economic revolution globally, leading to competition. Technical secondary schools, as organizations, have become facing changes and challenges that require them to excel in providing their services to community members. Thus, providing continuous learning opportunities for their individuals through the characteristics of a learning organization has become a necessity. These characteristics of a learning organization in the administration of technical secondary schools are what many educational organizations seek to develop their performance in order to face other changes that stand as obstacles in the path of future development.

From another perspective, reports and studies indicate a significant weakness in the level of administrative leaderships' awareness of the importance of applying the concepts of learning organizations.

From the above, the research problem can be presented in the following main question: How can the learning organization be a proposed approach for developing the administration of technical secondary schools in North Sinai Governorate?

This main question branches out into several sub-questions, which are:

- 1- What is the learning organization? What are its characteristics? And what is its role in developing the administration of technical secondary schools?
- 2- What is the theoretical framework for the administration of technical secondary schools in Egypt?
- 3- What is the reality of developing the administration of technical secondary schools in North Sinai Governorate?
- 4- What is the proposed vision for developing the administration of technical secondary schools in North Sinai Governorate in light of the learning organization?

Research Methodology and Tool

The current research employed the descriptive approach, which aims to describe the reality and events that occur in the present. It is concerned with the existing conditions, relationships, common practices, and opinions. This approach was chosen due to its suitability for the nature of the study, which requires collecting data and conducting statistical analysis to extract the desired results. The questionnaire was used as a tool for collecting this data to reveal the reality of the administration of technical secondary schools in the North Sinai Governorate.

Research Objectives

The current research aims to achieve the following

- Investigating the nature of the learning organization, its characteristics, models, and application mechanisms
- The theoretical framework for managing the learning organization in Egyptian technical secondary schools.
- Identifying and analyzing the reality of managing the learning organization in technical secondary schools in North Sinai Governorate.
- Developing a proposed approach for developing the management of the learning organization in technical secondary schools in North Sinai Governorate in light of the learning organization

Study Limitations

Human Limitations: The study was limited to a sample of (259) individuals, representing (13.28%) of the total study population, which consisted of (1951) individuals working in general secondary schools in North Sinai.

Spatial Limitations: The research was limited to technical secondary schools implementing the three- and five-year systems within the educational directorates of North Sinai Governorate.

Temporal Limitations: The study was applied during the second semester of the academic year 2021-2022.

Research Terms

The research includes the following main terms: The Learning Organization (Learning Organization)

Linguistically, the term refers to the organization of things or the arrangement of some of them in a structured and organized manner. Technically, it pertains to specific actions aimed at achieving competence and includes fundamental principles adhered to by its members

Senge defines it as organizations where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, and where new and expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning together. Kim defines it as an organization that has developed the capacity for continuous learning and adaptation, where all its members play an active role in identifying and solving the various related issues.

Developing School Management

Linguistically, the development of something means: moving it from one stage to a better stage or from one condition to a better condition, and the development process involves identifying strengths and addressing weaknesses in each component of the system .

It is designed and implemented, and it is an ongoing process of influential and connected factors, and at its core, it is based on specific standards and is implemented according to defined stages.

It is a planned process aimed at making changes in the desired thing and evaluating the extent of these changes.

Operationally, development is defined as: making changes at the practical level of administrative operations in technical secondary schools through developing proposed improvements to the existing school management system.

The importance of the learning organization lies in the following

Transfer of the Impact of Training and Improving Organizational Performance-1

There is a correlation between the learning organization and the transfer of training, which leads to improved performance and increased benefits under its umbrella, enabling organizations to remain competitive in the global landscape.

2-Assisting the Organization in Meeting the Requirements of Rapid Change in Today's World.

The rapid and continuous change in the economic, social, and political environment witnessed by today's world imposes, on organizations, a set of constraints that compel them to respond to it and work within its framework. This necessitates continuous learning of all new developments in the world of knowledge, skills, behavior, and keeping pace with them. Hence the importance of the learning organization in meeting the requirements of rapid change in today's world.

3-Increasing the Motivation of Organization Members

As the learning organization enhances the motivation of its employees to perform their duties, responsibilities, and tasks, and to advance in their work

Elements and Characteristics of the Learning Organization

This section attempts to address the following

Elements of the Learning Organization -1

The learning organization consists of three elements, which are

-Concepts: These include ideas, means, and techniques upon which the learning process depends, and which, in turn, contribute to increasing the employees' ability to innovate and renew

Proficiencies: These encompass skills, aptitudes, and experiences that result from the learning process and form positive attitudes that manifest in work behaviors.

Communication: This includes mutual relationships and interactions that focus on dialogue, cooperation, and the exchange and feedback of information.

The Organization's Strategies

Providing Continuous Learning Opportunities1 -

This means continuous growth through learning, experiences, and events, and this can be achieved at the individual level and at the level of the entire organizational team, which helps it achieve its goals. So, the individual or the team should not stop learning or developing. The effectiveness of continuous learning is based on the principle of continuous change in the way we think and act, for the sake of acquiring new concepts and knowledge. This strategy includes learning programs, e-learning, internet training, and developmental training related to project planning and the experiences of leading learning that have proven successful

-Encouraging the Principle of Dialogue and Inquiry 2

One of the priorities is to encourage dialogue and inquiry and the culture of asking open-ended questions, and that should be based on: being prepared to present difficult issues for discussion, as well as being open to receiving feedback at all levels. Dialogue is considered one of the highest social skills, and recognizing the value of something requires knowing its appropriate level. Dialogue is the work of prophets, scholars, thinkers, political leaders, and business leaders. It is the foundation of the father's success with his son.

Empowering Individuals with a Shared Collective Vision 3-

Where the organization's members participate in setting and owning the vision and implementing it collectively. Responsibilities are distributed based on clear decision-making, which motivates individuals to learn about what they will be held accountable for. The shared vision is the collective image of what the organization will be in the future, and it stems from a set of tools and methods for interaction with the aspirations and visions of all individuals inside and outside the school. It is expressed through deep dialogue with oneself and with others, and through building a shared perception of the future that they aspire to achieve together

There are a number of steps and stages that require implementation and achievement to reach a learning school, which are as follows

Encouraging and nurturing social learning*

- *Searching for successful practices among successful administrations and schools, and providing support, appreciation, and rewards

- *Accepting risk-taking and tolerating mistakes

- *Believing in individuals' ability to innovate

- *Building relationships and strengthening communication with others, both internally and externally

- *Encouraging initiatives for review and discussion

Knowledge for all, trust in all, and openness to all*

- *Evaluating the learning culture in the school to understand what works and what hinders its achievements

- *Encouraging positive interactions that occur within the school
- *Making the work environment a stimulating environment for thinking and searching for new ways and means to accomplish tasks
- *Encouraging competition and emphasizing free thinking
- Helping learners become resources for each other*

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